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A Study of Work Values of Secondary School Teachers in Relation to Gender, Type of School and Experience

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Abstract

Values play a vital role as it shapes man's activity. Values refer to objects or situations or activities which are liked or desired or approved by human beings. Values related to work include those motivationally relevant factors which energize and sustain human behaviour at their workplace. They guide attitudes and judgments, beyond immediate goal to more ultimate goals in work situation. The present paper tries to examine work values of secondary school teachers in relation to gender, type and experience. The sample consisted 400 secondary school teachers selected randomly from secondary schools situated in four districts of Haryana. Work values scale developed and standardized by the investigator was used. The result indicates that Work values of a teacher are directly related to their effective teaching and are also helpful in adjusting effectively with their school climate. There is a great impact of teachers' work values on students' performance.

Keywords: Teaching Effectiveness, Secondary School Teachers.

Introduction

Development of any country depends upon its education system. Good education system needs hard working and efficient teachers. A teacher must be physically, socially, emotionally and mentally healthy as well as have positive values. Values related to their work-boosting make any teacherable to complete their work smoothly without any hurdles. Education is universally accepted vehicle for the inculcation of human values and ethics.

Review of Literature

Work values denote a set of principles, which are applicable to a work or professions. It refers to the principles of values, directly or indirectly applicable to the work and conduct of individuals working as professionals. Work values motivate, sustain, direct and control the human behaviour. Every work or profession has their own values to regulate its terms, conditions, norms and quality of service to be rendered. In this changing society, the work, nature and responsibility of a teacher are also change. Dealing with values and moral issues is recognized as an integral part of teachers' roles (Alexander Mohan 2016). This also affects their values and values pattern.

Teacher helps students in realization of their goals and fulfilment of their moral, social, aesthetical, educational and psychological needs. Super defined work-values as- "they permeate all aspects of life; they concern life's goals in some cases they seem to be related with needs, drives and attitudes."

Marie Charlotte (1983) examined the work values of secondary school teachers: A comparative study by teaching assignment. The sample of the study consisted 220 Oregon teachers of 7th through 12th grades, located in 12 upper Willamette Valley rural and urban secondary schools. The Ohio work values inventory was used on the sample. It was observed that secondary school teachers varied by the gender on four values. Female teachers placed higher value on self-realization and males placed higher value on object orientation, solitude, and prestige values. The means score for female were greater than means for male on altruism, task satisfaction, and self-realization but were less than the mean scores for males on control, money, solitude and prestige.

Reddy and Reddy (2003) conducted a study on gender and work value preferences: A study on I.T. professional in Chennai city. On the sample of 107 administering a questionnaire containing-28 items. The

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researcher found that 10 males give more importance to "authority and status" and "travel abroad" in comparison to females. Whereas females give more importance to "congenial social relationships" and facilitating work environment. The significant gender effect was observed on these mentioned work values and not the other remaining work values.

Singh P. (2005) studied relationship between stress and work values among secondary level female teachers. The objective of the study was to study the relationship between stress and work values among the secondary school female teachers. In this study causal comparative and co-relational type of descriptive research was used. The sample for the study constituted of 150 secondary level female teachers from five schools of Allahabad. Teacher stress scale by K.S. Mishra and Poonam Singh and Work value differential by D. Chandra tool were used by the researcher and it was found that (1) values related to work such as economic return, social service, power, independence and adventure were found to be negatively and significantly correlated with stress. (2) There was no significant relationship between stress and work values.

Justification of the study

The present time is the age of knowledge explosion and the learner is over burdened to perform significantly in any sphere of life. It is rightly said that student's positive interest and attitude in their field can be shaped up only through a teacher. So work values of teachers are very important. Their values will not only influence their academic and teaching performance but would have enormous impact on students. This study will add some new information to existing knowledge of work values of teachers which would help them for enhancing effective teaching learning environment.

Operational Definition of Term Used

Work Values

In this study work value is related to teaching skills of the class room like planning, presentation, flexibility and evaluation etc. are centered on teacher classroom behaviour in relation to student behaviour

Table No.1

Significance Difference between work values of male and female secondary school teachers

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Male	93.936	203	22.02	5.72
Female	88.881	203	22.58	

It can be observed that mean score of work values among male and female secondary school teachers are 93.936 and 88.881 with respect SD= 22.02 and 22.58. In the table the t-value is 5.72 which is more than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 level. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between work values

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and organizational climate. Investigator used work value scale which includes four components as Values Related to self, preparation, Work environment and Setting of work and activities developed by herself.

Objectives of the study

1. To study the work values of the secondary school teachers.
2. To compare the different work values of secondary school teachers with respect to gender.
3. To compare the different work values of secondary school teachers with respect to school.
4. To compare the different work values of secondary school teachers with respect to experience wise.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between work values of secondary school teachers with respect to gender
2. There is no significant difference between work values of secondary school teachers with respect to type of school.
3. There is no significant difference between work values of secondary school teachers with respect to experience.

Research Methodology

Keeping in view the nature of the present study the descriptive survey method was used. For the collection of data the researcher selected 400 secondary school teachers through multistage probability sampling technique. A self-developed work values scale used by researcher in this study. In this study descriptive and inferential statistics are used such as mean, standard deviation, t-test, f-test and coefficient of correlation (r).

Delimitation of the Study

The present study confined to:

1. The state of Haryana only.
2. Three districts of Haryana state.
3. 400 secondary school teachers only.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

of male and female secondary school teachers' is rejected, which shows that male secondary school teachers have high work values than female secondary school teachers because females are diverted by their responsibilities (home, work place) than male. This finding is supported by Dixit and Sharma's (1969)

Table No.2

Significance difference between work values of male and female secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience

gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Male	89.68	69	23.52	2.00
Female	87.89	69	22.38	

It can be observed that mean score of work values of male, and female secondary school

teachers having 0-5 years teaching experience are 89.68 and 87.89 with respect to SD=23.52 and 22.38.

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in the table the t-value is 2.00 which is above than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 level. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant

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difference between work values of male and female secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience' is rejected.

Table no.3

Significance difference between work values of male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 teaching experience

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Male	92.86	69	22.56	6.58
Female	60.65	69	40.08	

It can be observed that mean score of work values of male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 years teaching experience are 92.86 and 60.65 with respect to SD= 22.56 and 40.08. In the table the t-value is 6.58 which is more than tabulated

value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 level. Thus our hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between work values of male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 teaching experience' is rejected.

Table no.4: Significance difference between work values of male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Male	96.71	66	21.91	3.45
Female	91.24	66	20.91	

It can be observed that mean score of work values of male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience are 96.71 and 91.24 with respect to SD= 21.91 and 20.91. In the table the t-value is 6.58 which is more than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 level. In the table the t-value is 3.45 which is

more than tabulated value 1.98. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between work values of male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience' is rejected as male secondary school teachers are comparatively more learned persons at this stage than female secondary school teachers.

Table no.5: Significance difference between work values of government and private secondary school teachers

Type of school	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Government	87.732	202	22.49	5.11
Private	95.460	202	21.50	

It can be observed that mean score of work values of government and private secondary school teachers are 87.732 and 95.460 with respect to SD= 22.49 and 21.50. In the table the t-value is 6.58 which is more than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 level. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between work values

of government and private secondary school teachers' is rejected which shows that private secondary school teachers have high work values because of government policies such as transfer and withholding promotions. This finding analysed by Mittal (1989).

Table no.6: Significance difference between work values of government and private secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience

Type of school	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Government	83.55	68	21.16	6.55
Private	97.10	68	20.73	

It can be observed that mean score of work values of government and private secondary school teachers having 0-5 years teaching experience are 83.55 and 97.10 with respect to SD= 21.16 and 20.73. In the table the t-value is 6.55 which is more than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 level. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no

significant difference between work values of government and private secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience' is rejected which shows that private secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience have high work values as they get more comfortable working conditions than government secondary school teachers.

Table no.7: Significance difference between work values of government and private secondary school teachers having 5-10 teaching experience

Type of school	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
government	86.95	67	23.77	4.37
Private	95.04	67	22.20	

It can be observed that mean score of work values of government and private secondary school teachers having 5-10 years teaching experience are 86.95 and 95.04 with respect to SD= 23.77 and 22.20. In the table the t-value is 4.37 which is more than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 level. Thus our hypothesis i.e. 'there is no

significant difference between work values of government and private Secondary school teachers having 5-10 years teaching experience' is rejected which shows that private secondary school teachers have high work values as they have more comfortable environment than government secondary school teachers having 5-10 years teaching experience.

Table no.8: Significance difference between work Values of government and private secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience

Type of school	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
government	93.28	66	21.54	1.02
Private	94.68	66	21.59	

It can be observed that mean score of work values of government and private secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience are 93.28 and 94.68 with respect to SD=21.54 and 21.59. In the table the t-value is 1.02 which is less than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is not significant at 0.05 level. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no

significant difference between work values of government and private Secondary school teachers having above 10 teaching experience' is accepted which shows that both government and private secondary school teachers have equal work values (Grusky 1966).

Table no.9: Significance difference between work values of government male and female secondary school teachers

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Government Male	90.87	101	21.56	5.50
Government Female	84.59	101	23.07	

It can be observed that mean score of work values of government male and female secondary school teachers are 90.87 and 84.59 with respect to SD= 21.56 and 23.07. In the table the t-value is 5.50 which is more than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 level. Thus our hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between work values of government male and female secondary school

teachers' is rejected which shows that government male secondary school teachers have high work values than female secondary school teachers as government male secondary school teachers have more financial opportunities and responsibilities than female secondary school teachers.

Table no.10: Significance difference between work values of government male and female of secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience

Type of school	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
government male	85.76	34	20.07	2.89
government female	81.35	34	22.28	

It can be observed that mean score of work values of government male and female secondary school teachers are 85.76 and 81.35 with respect to SD= 21.56 and 23.07. In the table the t-value is 2.89 which is more than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 level. Thus our hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between work values

of government male and female secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience' is rejected which shows that government male secondary school teachers have high work values as they are more concerned about their work than female secondary school teachers.

Table no.11: Significance difference between work values of government male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 teaching experience

Type of school	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
government male	92.24	33	22.59	4.63
government female	82.33	33	24.28	

It can be observed that mean score of work values among government male and female of secondary school teachers having 5-10 years teaching experience are 92.24 and 82.33 with respect to standard deviations 22.59 and 24.28. In the table the t-value is 4.63 which is more than tabulated value

1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 level. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between work values of government male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 teaching experience' is rejected.

Table no.12: Significance difference between work values of government male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience

Type of school	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
government male	95.54	33	21.29	3.81
government female	91.03	33	21.88	

It can be observed that mean score of work values of government male and female of secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience are 95.54 and 91.03 with respect to standard deviations 21.29 and 21.88. In the table the t-value is 3.81 which is more than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 level. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference

between work values of government male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience' is rejected which shows that government male secondary school teachers have high work values as they are more experienced than government female secondary school teachers.

Table no.13: Significance difference between work values of private male and female secondary school teachers

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Private Male	96.97	102	22.15	2.86
Private Female	93.12	102	21.37	

It can be observed that mean score of work values among private male and female secondary school teachers are 96.97 and 93.12 with respect to SD= 22.15 and 21.37. In the table the t-value is 2.86 which is more than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 level. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between work values of

private male and female secondary school teachers' is rejected which shows that private male secondary school teachers have high work values than private female secondary school teachers, as they have more opportunities to make achievements than female teachers.

Table no.14: Significance difference between work values of private male and female of secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience.

Type of school	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
private male	97.77	35	22.08	2.04
Private female	94.25	35	20.87	

It can be observed that mean score of work values of private male and female of secondary school teachers having 0-5 years teaching experience are 97.77 and 94.25 with respect to standard deviations 22.08 and 20.87. In the table the t-value is

2.04 which is more than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 level. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between work values of private male and female secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience' is rejected.

Table no.15 Significance difference between work values of private male and female of secondary school teachers having 5-10 teaching experience

Type of school	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
private male	95.35	34	22.02	.99
Private female	93.55	34	23.44	

it can be observed that mean score of work values among private male and female of secondary school teachers having 5-10 years teaching experience are 95.35 and 93.55 with respect to SD=22.02 and 23.44. In the table the t-value is .99 which is less than

tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is not significant at 0.05 level. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between work values of private male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 teaching experience' is accepted.

Table no.16

Significance difference between work values of private male and female of secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience

Type of school	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
private male	97.87	33	22.77	2.92
Private female	91.48	33	20.18	

It can be observed that mean score of work values of private male and female of secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience are 97.87 and 91.48 with respect to SD= 22.77 and 20.18. In the table the t-value is 2.92 which is more than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 level. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between work values of private male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience' is rejected which shows that private male secondary school teachers have high work values than female secondary school teachers because male secondary school teachers have more opportunities to involve in decision making which make their work value positively high than female teachers.

Findings

1. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of male and female secondary school teachers and male secondary school teachers have high work values than female secondary school teachers because females are diverted by their responsibilities (home, work place) than male.

2. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of male and female secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience and male secondary school teachers have high work values than female secondary school teachers.

3. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 teaching experience and male secondary school teachers have high work values than female secondary school teachers.

4. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience and male secondary school teachers have high work values than female secondary school teachers.

5. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of government and private secondary school teachers and private secondary school teachers have high work values than government secondary school teachers because of government policies such as

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- transfer and withholding promotions. This finding analyzed by Mittal (1989).
6. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of government and private secondary school teachers having 0-5 years teaching experience and private secondary school teachers have high work values than govt. secondary school teachers.
 7. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of government and private secondary school teachers having 5-10 years teaching experience and private secondary school teachers have high work values than govt. secondary school teachers.
 8. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of government and private secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience and work values of govt. and private secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience are almost equal which shows that both government and private secondary school teachers have equal work values.
 9. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of government male and female secondary school teachers and government male secondary school teachers have high work values than female secondary school teachers.
 10. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of government male and female secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience and government male secondary school teachers have high work values than female secondary school teachers.
 11. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of government male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 teaching experience and government male secondary school teachers have high work values than female secondary school teachers.
 12. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of government male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience and government male secondary school teachers have high work values than female secondary school teachers.
 13. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of private male and female secondary school teachers and private male secondary school teachers have high work values than female secondary school teachers.
 14. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of private male and female secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience and private male secondary school teachers have high work values than female secondary school teachers.
 15. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of private male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 teaching experience and private male secondary school teachers have high work values than female secondary school teachers.

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16. It was found that there is significant difference between work values of private male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience and private male secondary school teachers have high work values than female secondary school teachers.

Conclusion

On the basis of above findings it is said that male secondary school teachers have more positive work values than female secondary school teachers because females are more diverted by their responsibilities (home, work place) than male. It is also found that private secondary school teachers have high work values because teachers of government schools feel difficulties to cope up with government policies such as transfer and withholding promotions. This finding also supported by the finding of Mittal (1989).

Suggestions for Further Studies

1. The present study is delimited to state of Haryana state only which can be conducted in other states also.
2. The present study is conducted on secondary school teachers only and this study can be conducted on different population such as primary, middle and university level school teachers
3. The present study is delimited to 400 secondary school teachers only which can be conducted with a large sample.
4. Similar study can be conducted on other variables also such as teacher efficacy, job stress and job satisfaction etc.

References

- Alexander Mohan (2016), *role of teachers in inculcating values among students, National conference on "value education through teacher education", vol-1, no. 2.*
- Aftab Mariya (2013). *An investigation into the relationship among teacher's occupational stress, job satisfaction, work values and pupil control ideology, department of Education, Aligarh Muslim university Aligarh (U.P) - India.*
- Brocne, La Vonne Anloinctte (2001). *On faith and work: the relationship between religiosity and work-values. Dissertation abstracts international, June 2000, vol.62 (12), 4069-A.*
- Dixit and Sharma (1969). *Incorporation by students of teachers values: A study of the student-teacher relationship. Indian educational research, vol. 4 (2), Pp-89-96.*
- Ganga (2009) *work values and job satisfaction, Karnatka, journal of agriculture science. Vol.22 (5), 1143-1144.*
- Geren and Brenda (2002). *Exploring work values difference in the transitional Economy of China: University, dissertation abstracts international, 63 (05), 1902-A.*
- Grusky (1966). *Organizational commitment and work values of teachers and leadership behaviour of heads of high schools in Bangalor (India) and Sanandaj (Iran)- A comparative study, Synopsis.*

E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

- Jolides and Yesodhara (2009). Work values among high school teachers in India, Iran influence of age and subject taught internet.*
- Lovat Terence (2005). Values education and teachers' work: a quality teaching perspective, The University of Newcastle, NSW 2308, Australia.*
- Marie Charlotte (1983). The work values of secondary teachers: a comparative study by teaching assignment, Portland State University, Dissertations and Theses, paper 3271.*
- Mittal (1989). An exploratory study of teachers' motivation to work and its relationship with school climate of schools, M.Phil., Edu. JamiaMillia*
- Moshahid M. (2017).A study of adjustment among goeernment and private secondary school teachers. Educational Quest: an Int. J. of Education and applied social science, vol.8 (1), pp-157-162.*

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- Reddy and Reddy (2003). Gender and work value preferences: A study on I.T. professional in Chennai city. Indian journal for applied Psychology (Madras) vol. 40, pp. 33-39.*
- Singh, P. (2005). Relationship between Stress and Work Values among Secondary Level Female Teachers, Ram-Eesh Journal of Education, Vol. 2(2), 58- 60.*
- Spence and Janet G (2003). The relationship between cooperative education student work values and work site manager's referent power, Dissertation abstracts international, vol. 64 (04), 1231-A.*
<http://www.ncert.nic.in/html/pdf/publication/journal2008>.
- <http://network.bepress.com/explore/education/health>
<http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/19603/11050/>.
- <http://www.curriculum.edu.au/verve/resources/values/>